

WAYS OF FORMING RESEARCH ABILITY IN FUTURE PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL TEACHERS

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Annotation: One of important problems of modern education is education of a creative person. Sphere of the higher education lastly directed to from scientific world outlook of young people. In this article are shined creative and practical aspects of formation of research skills at pupils and students.

Key words: training, competence, research competence, future teacher.

Higher education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2030 development consultation to improve the quality of education based on the provision of a solid integration of science, education and production arising from the production of social spheres and economic sectors without higher education, capable personnel . production, effective organization of scientific and innovative activities, development of economic development, President of Uzbekistan dated July 11, 2019 No. PQ-4391 "On measures to introduce new management methods into the system of higher and secondary special education It was produced due to the implementation of the decision "on" and this consensus is a proof that the work carried out in all fields in independent Uzbekistan is recognized by the world community today. From this point of view, in our country, attention is paid to the development of the field of science and education at the level of state policy, and special attention is paid to the fundamental reform of education.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoev, in his speech entitled "Focusing on enlightenment today is more important than ever before" said that "Sustainable socio-economic development is impossible without innovative development, large-scale scientific and technical cooperation and new "It is

impossible to imagine without the introduction of technology, science and technical achievements," he admits.

Nowadays, it is impossible to imagine a teacher of a preschool education organization with a high level of spirituality in isolation from daily pedagogical research activities. The educator of the future preschool educational organization can achieve modernization of education only if he realizes that his scientific and pedagogical research works will have a positive effect on the development of the state and society.

To increase the quality level of training of MTT educators in our country, to create the necessary conditions for the training of highly qualified specialists based on international standards, to establish close cooperation relations between each higher educational institution with the world's leading scientific and educational institutions, to bring international attention to the educational process wide introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and teaching-methodical materials based on educational standards, development of modern professional knowledge and creative abilities of students, scientific-pedagogical personnel, effective use of interactive methods in working with young audiences issues were defined as the main tasks of quality improvement and fundamental improvement of the level of higher education in accordance with the priorities of the Development Strategy.

In the context of modern education, there are many opportunities to solve promising problems. In particular, the purpose expressed in phrases and concepts such as "Innovative technologies", "Information technologies", "Pedagogical technologies", "advanced pedagogical technologies" is aimed at training modern scientific pedagogical personnel and ensuring the quality of education.

Pedagogue I. Zakirov scientifically and theoretically justified the increase of creative activity of young people based on the application of pedagogical technologies to the educational process. According to the analysis of the above scientific researches, modern technologies that increase the capabilities of mankind

in terms of information production also mark the quality of the intellectual potential of an intelligent society. Such processes are also the scientific and technical basis for the regular development of the information industry.

Operation on the basis of information technologies ensures the efficiency of solving the following tasks: processing information about the source and the process taking place in it; to regularly receive periodically updated information about the progress of processes and to conduct intermediate controls based on them; need to be able to respond to, process and manage voluntary current requests on the fly.

So, today is characterized by a bold step towards an information society. In addition, informatization is a whole set of tools and conditions for the development of information processes, and implies a broader approach to computerization, which includes the creation of an appropriate technical basis, the development of organizational and economic reforms. On this basis, information bases for the functioning of various social systems are created. Based on the above considerations, it can be said that directing young people to scientific research in the continuous education system should be carried out as a targeted, technological process. In addition, it is important that the educator of MTT has the ability to apply all the theoretical knowledge, pedagogy and psychology information acquired in the higher school in the process of practical activity.

In our country, comprehensive attention to the field of preschool education has reached the level of state policy today. The content of a number of decisions and decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is aimed at fundamentally improving the quality of education in the field. On July 18, 2018, the new "First and State requirements for the development of preschool children" was approved. In accordance with these state requirements, the levels of knowledge, skills and abilities of preschool children, their comprehensive development and readiness for school education are determined.

The content and methods of preschool education are organized in an environment where the processes of the formation of the child's personality and his

recognition as an independent person take place. Preschool period is a period when a child develops motivation, self-expression, building, self-realization, desire to do something, aspiration. During this period, the foundation is created for the development of the child as a person. It is in the preschool period that universal human qualities are formed that help the child to be successful in all future activities and in life in general. All this develops through the personal activity of the child in drawing, building, music and other activities. The main task of preschool education is to create a positive psychological microclimate and conditions in the institution in order to ensure the maximum development of each child's personality and his preparation for the next stage of development. What is required from parents and educators is great patience, love and a scientifically based approach to child rearing. As a result of proper upbringing, the child is ready to think independently and take a bold step into life. The peculiarity of child-oriented education is that the child is formed in accordance with his capabilities, potential, and characteristics of his nature, not according to someone's wishes and orders. The knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by the child in preschool education lay the foundation for his future success in school education.

The knowledge and concepts given to the child in preschool education, including the formation of study skills, serve to develop the child's mental abilities and overcome major difficulties in school education in the future. It is of particular importance to use the method of a systematic approach and to use the technology of processing the resulting information complex in the effective organization of scientific research in the continuous education system.

Therefore, a person who is worthy of this society and actively participates in its development should conduct scientific research as a specialist, divide the obtained information into systems, and know the methods of choosing optimal options for problem-specific ideas and technical solutions. On the other hand, research and creative thinking require a modern specialist to be able to choose the optimal solution to promising tasks by using the achievements of science, and to conduct

experiments and tests in his practical work. Therefore, the current state of the education system and the requirements for it show that the optimal management of the higher education process is one of the urgent problems.

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